

MIMO versus Phased Array Antenna Systems for 5G Mobile Communication Systems

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Abstract: *Antenna technology is a critical component of mobile communications. With every upgrade in generation of mobile communications, antenna technology has been ameliorating in performance, starting from simple omnidirectional antennas for analog communication in the first generation, to digital antenna arrays (smart antenna) in second and third generation to MIMO antenna arrays in fourth generation. Fifth generation of mobile communications is expected to have significant increase in data rates, capacity and number of users. This demands an advanced antenna technology capable of meeting the requirements. This paper aims to compare the performance of two of the existing antenna technologies: MIMO and phased array and highlight their usage in 5G technologies.*

Keywords: *MIMO; Phased array; 5G; Hybrid beamforming; Channel state estimation*

I. INTRODUCTION

The exceptional increase in usage of mobile devices has resulted in new technologies and standards. The fifth generation of mobile communication systems represent a significant growth in number of end devices and data rates, with the advent of Internet of Things. It aims to achieve latency of the order of milliseconds and serve almost 300,000 end devices per access node, with more efficient user experience. It also aims to provide D2D (device to device) communication, where direct communication between devices without the need for routing through network infrastructure is possible. Antenna technology plays a crucial role in the development of 5G mobile communication, enabling better coverage and higher data rates. Two major technologies: MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) and beam forming using phased arrays are capable of catering the needs of the fifth generation wireless communication systems. The “all-band-to-5G” transition necessitate antenna systems which could support all bands. Further, the antennas must be flexible enough to adopt to diversified applications. Also, single antenna must support C Band and MM Wave spectrum resources to

support 5G NTN features. The antenna must be designed to support all band configuration and beam coverage must be precise to cater to the applications such that the beam energy is concentrated on desired areas and at the same time, it must not cause interference to non-desired coverage areas. The antennas must support multiuser beam forming, allowing multiuser beams to share the time and frequency domain resources to maximize the spectral efficiency. Accurate null steering control on antennas would help to suppress the interference caused by resource sharing. Further, the antennas have be designed such that the maximum radiated energy must be concentrated on the desired areas. Hence there is a need to compare the two major antenna technologies to study the feasibility of their use in 5G. The paper is organized as follows: Section II deals with the concepts of MIMO and Massive MIMO. Section III deals with the concept of phased arrays and beamforming using them. Section IV deals with the concept of hybrid beamforming in 5G mobile communication. The paper is concluded in Section V.

II. MIMO

MIMO is wireless communication methods where multiple transmit and receive antennas are used to improve the capacity of a link. It utilizes the concept of multipath propagation, where a single radio signal can reach the receiver via different paths. MIMO splits a signal into several low data rate sub-signals and transmits them via spatially separated antennas using the same frequency channel. Due to multipath propagation, they are received via different paths at the receiver. The receiver separates these signals into parallel streams, which are then processed to recover the original signal. MIMO offers a significant increase in channel capacity without any additional bandwidth and power consumption.

The channel throughput can be increased linearly with the addition of transmit and receive antenna pairs. MIMO technology has been standardized for 4G mobile communication networks and now in commercial use. 4G-LTE has different MIMO schemes for uplink and downlink. LTE downlink schemes assume a 2x2

